

An adaptive boundary model for defining regimes on prediction markets

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Abstract

Volatility greatly increase risk for the trader, the paper seeks to find a way of understanding the current regimes expected oscillation, this in turn gives a better insight into the current market conditions, thus gaining better insight into the associated risk. Prediction markets are still in their infant phase compared to traditional exchanges, thus making research about risk management limited. The paper introduces an adaptive boundary model for defining regimes, which is found to be useful across not only prediction markets, however it also employs useful across traditional and crypto exchanges, as well as a general analytics tool.

Keywords: Market microstructure, Prediction markets, Regime detection, Adaptive boundaries, Risk management

1 Introduction

The paper seeks to find a way of defining regimes on prediction markets. This is done with the goal of understanding the current market conditions, and expected oscillation. First it is important to understand what prediction markets are and why they offer a unique way to market make on their exchanges.

Prediction markets have gained ample popularity in recent years as they offer an interesting take on the derivatives market. Markets like Kalshi or Polymarket offer users the ability to purchase contracts with a yes or no outcomes. The prediction markets function largely the same as regular exchanges, as they allow for users to post both bid and ask quotes. This means for each contract bought or sold, there has to be a seller and a buyer. These contracts are based on real events like a football game, or a presidential election. Each event is refereed to as a market and has its own contract price, this can be thought of as a ticker on a traditional market. Each contract on prediction markets cost between 1c and 99c, corresponding to the probability of the event outcome. Due to the probabilistic approach to contract pricing on prediction markets, the price often makes erratic changes if new information is introduced about a given market. These price jumps can be seen as information jumps, as it is price "jumping" to new information. These price jumps will be refereed to as information jumps throughout this paper. Thus these information jumps can make it difficult for interpreting the risk of ones position in the market.

Therefore the paper introduces a regime defining model for prediction markets. The model presented in the paper works strictly based off market derived information. This is done because it is difficult to gain an insight into the current market regime with exogenous data. At the current time it is not know that such a framework for prediction markets, has been presented by any public papers yet. The model has other applications, which will be mentioned, however performing simulations of these applications is outside the scope of this paper.

The paper will then seek to contribute to the unknown field of defining regimes on prediction markets. Therefore the model tries to offer an adaptive risk management model for trader on these markets. It also seeks to understand the different regimes on prediction markets and how new information impacts the current regime and how regimes behave after these information jumps.

The model does not offer any form of trading decision, that is to be inferred by the user. It also does not give an optimal price or optimal trading time. It does not assume stationarity and does not assume that markets move with a fixed volatility. Thus this is a regime defining model that offers information about market regimes not a trading model. The model does also not offer the optimal place to quote it simply, acts as a regime definer. In section 4 applications will be discussed

in a trading sense, however it is understood that it is a byproduct application of the model. The main application of the model is to understand regimes on prediction market.

2 Theory and model

Prediction markets function like regular stock exchanges (Bürge et al., 2025). They allow users to quote both a bid and an ask side. Prediction markets like traditional exchanges allow for both retail and institutional users to quote prices, as it is not a restricted market. Regimes on prediction markets rarely persist for an extended period. This occurs because information about the event, change the market occupants perceived probability of the outcomes, thus causing an information jump.

Figure 1: Picture of kalshi.com: Bournemouth vs Sunderland EPL game 28/2/2026(note the probability does not sum to 100 since there is also an outcome of tie which can be quoted by users).

In Figure 1 an example of an information jump is observed. This particular information jump happened after a goal was scored. This essentially flipped the market occupants perceived probabilities of each team winning. Thus a model for defining market regime is important for understanding how prediction markets function from market derived information. It also employs important for informing traders about their current place in the market.

2.1 Theory

The model seeks to define regimes, or price intervals, where it defines the current market behavior and what can oscillation can be expected. The model defines an upper and a lower boundary from the current price, historical volatility and historical variance. This ensures it defines it based on market derived time series data, and not exogenous data. The current price is arbitrarily defined, and can be defined as the last quote, a self defined fair price, the mid quote or anything else deemed fit at representing the current price. The volatility and variance weighted boundaries assist in making the boundaries adjusted to the historical deviation. This can be understood as for example: If the chosen market has experienced high historical volatility the boundaries will be wider, as it is considered a high volatility regime, thus making price oscillation more accepted by the current regime. A regimes time interval is defined as the point in time where the boundaries time series data begin, to the point where price exceeds either the upper or lower boundary. If the current price exceeds the upper or lower boundary, the current regime becomes redundant, and is considered conditionally irrelevant to understanding future market dynamics. This will be detailed further in section 2.3. Providing a scaler for adjusting desired oscillation is also important. This is important for making the model more adjustable and be able to adhere to the users needs. Following these requirements the model then seeks to provides a framework for defining regimes on prediction markets. For more information about regime switching processes please refer to (Van Beek et al., 2020).

2.2 General notation

This section will cover and explain the general notation used in the model.

2.2.1 Boundary notation

First it is important to explain the notation used in the model. In the model the upper and lower boundary are denoted as such,

$$L_t$$

For the lower boundary, and

$$U_t$$

for the upper boundary.

L_t and U_t have two states respectively, I and RS_i . These are the notation for the initial, and the regime switch state. This is done so the two states are easily differentiable. The i in RS_i denotes the number of the current regime shift. This is so a regime can be added, when a regime shift occurs in a RS_i state. There is only one initial state, thus it is not denoted with i . Thus each each boundary has two states denoted as such, starting with the initial state,

$$L_t^I$$

For the lower boundary, and

$$U_t^I$$

for the upper boundary.

The notation for the regime switched state,

$$L_t^{RS_i}$$

For the lower boundary, and

$$U_t^{RS_i}$$

for the upper boundary.

2.2.2 Price notation

The model takes the arbitrarily defined fair price as an input. In the model the price is written as p_t . It is also understood that p_t must be in \mathbb{R} . It can be denoted like this:

$$p_t \subseteq \mathbb{R}$$

For the uses in prediction markets p_t will be defined as a number in subset $X \subseteq \mathbb{R}$. Where X is a set from 1 -99. It can be denoted as such:

$$X = \{X \in \mathbb{R} | 1 \leq X \leq 99\}$$

$$p_t \subseteq X$$

2.2.3 Variance and volatility notation

The model uses variance and volatility estimation to compute the each boundary. The initial and the regime switch state's variance and volatility estimations are denoted with n and m respectively. This is done because of the different look back times that each state can have. The variance and volatility estimations are denoted like this, starting with initial state variance:

$$\overline{\sigma_{nYZ}^2} = \overline{\sigma_{nYZ}^2}(s, n, t) = \frac{1}{t - (t - n)} \int_{t-n}^t \sigma_{YZ}^2(s) ds$$

For the initial state, and

$$\overline{\sigma_{mYZ}^2} = \overline{\sigma_{mYZ}^2}(s, m, t) = \frac{1}{t - (t - m)} \int_{t-m}^t \sigma_{YZ}^2(s) ds$$

for the regime switched state.

And the volatility notation starting with initial state,

$$\overline{\sigma_{nYZ}} = \overline{\sigma_{nYZ}}(s, n, t) = \frac{1}{t - (t - n)} \int_{t-n}^t \sigma_{YZ}(s) ds$$

for the initial state, and

$$\overline{\sigma_{mYZ}} = \overline{\sigma_{mYZ}}(s, m, t) = \frac{1}{t - (t - m)} \int_{t-m}^t \sigma_{YZ}(s) ds$$

for the regime switched state.

This leaves us with the mean of the variance and volatility over the desired period. It is important to note that any kind of variance and volatility estimation can be used, although in this paper Yang Zhang variance and volatility estimation are the ones that is being used, hence the notation YZ (Yang and Zhang, 2000). Yang Zhang variance and volatility estimations are denoted as such starting with variance,

$$\sigma^2 = V'o + k'V'c + (1 - k')\overline{V}$$

for variance and,

$$\sigma = \sqrt{V'o + k'V'c + (1 - k')\overline{V}}$$

for volatility.

2.3 Model

From the theory and notation, the following model has been created.

2.3.1 Model Base formula

Thus the base formula for the model is presented. Note this version is not denoted with I and RS_i . The base formula is denoted as such, where $\lambda > 0$,

$$L_t = L(p_t, \lambda, n, t) = (1 - \frac{1}{t - (t - n)} \int_{t-n}^t \sigma^2_{YZ} \lambda) (\log p_t - \frac{1}{t - (t - n)} \int_{t-n}^t \sigma_{YZ})$$

and,

$$U_t = U(p_t, \lambda, n, t) = (1 + \frac{1}{t - (t - n)} \int_{t-n}^t \sigma^2_{YZ} \lambda) (\log p_t + \frac{1}{t - (t - n)} \int_{t-n}^t \sigma_{YZ})$$

or,

$$L_t = L(p_t, \lambda, n, t) = (1 - \frac{1}{n} \int_{t-n}^t \sigma^2_{YZ} \lambda) (\log p_t - \frac{1}{n} \int_{t-n}^t \sigma_{YZ})$$

and,

$$U_t = U(p_t, \lambda, n, t) = (1 + \frac{1}{n} \int_{t-n}^t \sigma^2_{YZ} \lambda) (\log p_t + \frac{1}{n} \int_{t-n}^t \sigma_{YZ})$$

finally,

$$L_t = L(p_t, \lambda, n, t) = (1 - \overline{\sigma^2_{YZ}} \lambda) (\log p_t - \overline{\sigma_{YZ}})$$

and,

$$U_t = U(p_t, \lambda, n, t) = (1 + \overline{\sigma^2_{YZ}} \lambda) (\log p_t + \overline{\sigma_{YZ}})$$

The model has the parameters p_t, λ, n, t , which are used to specify the model for the users needs. The input n is for the look back time. The look back time is defined as how much of the previous regimes time series price data the user wishes to include in the model. This will be explained deeper in 2.3.2. t is the input for time and denotes where to take the current price from and defines the historical data interval. It also defines when in the time series data the $t - n$ look back should start.

The first part of the formula $(1 \pm \overline{\sigma^2_{YZ}} \lambda)$ acts a percentage scaler to the second part. λ is used as a scaler to the $\overline{\sigma^2_{YZ}}$, as to widen or narrow the boundaries. This functionality gives the user the ability to adjust how much risk wanted to take on, since allowing for more oscillation, allows for more risk to the traders positions. Thus the λ can fundamentally change the change the function. This parameter makes sure that the the user has control over the boundaries and how much oscillation should be allow in each regime, making sure the user has more control, and does not rely on predetermined parameters. Note that the removal of $\overline{\sigma^2_{YZ}}$ can give the user more control over the boundaries, denoted, $(1 \pm \lambda)$, although that is outside the scope of this paper. Also Note that $\lambda > 0$ or else the boundaries will switch place. Differentiating with respect to λ gives us a better idea of what the first part does to the second part,

$$\frac{dL_t}{d\lambda} = \overline{\sigma^2_{YZ}} (\log p_t - \overline{\sigma_{YZ}})$$

and,

$$\frac{dU_t}{d\lambda} = \overline{\sigma^2_{YZ}} (\log p_t + \overline{\sigma_{YZ}})$$

Therefore it is found that the first part acts as a variance scaler to the second part. From this we can understand the boundaries width mainly get decided by the second part of the equation. This can be inferred since the second part get scaled the variances size, thus making the amount it get scaled limited by the $\overline{\sigma^2}_{YZ}$ size. This means λ is an important parameter deciding with of the boundaries, however the main scaler of the boundaries is $\overline{\sigma}_{YZ}$.

The second part of the equation ($\log p_t \pm \overline{\sigma}_{YZ}$) is subtracting or adding the standard deviation from the log-price. This serves to move the boundary $\pm\sigma$, as the model deems this an acceptable amount of movement, for the price to stay within the current regime. Taking the derivative with respect to p_t , it can be observed how it gets scaled by the first part,

$$\frac{dL_t}{dp_t} = (1 - \overline{\sigma^2}_{YZ}\lambda) \frac{1}{p_t}$$

and,

$$\frac{dU_t}{dp_t} = (1 + \overline{\sigma^2}_{YZ}\lambda) \frac{1}{p_t}$$

From this it is found that the boundary gets scaled by the part the first part of function.

The model takes the log of p_t because $\overline{\sigma^2}_{YZ}$ and $\overline{\sigma}_{YZ}$ are already in log-space, thus p_t needs to be in log-space for it to be additive. This also means that the function outputs a number in log-space. if it is wished to return the boundaries to the original price index, the *exp* of L_t and U_t can be taken to get the boundaries back to the original price index. Which can be denoted like this,

$$\exp(L_t)$$

and,

$$\exp(U_t)$$

2.3.2 Initial and regime switched state notation

Initial and regime switched state use notation, I and RS_i respectively. The I and RS_i states use n and m respectively for their look back times. This is done because when a regime shift occurs the previous regime is considered conditionally irrelevant, thus it doesn't represent the current state of the market anymore. Therefore m needs to have a shorter look back time than n . It is also important to understand that we must have $m \leq n \leq t$. To understand this a lemma is presented.

Lemma 2.1 *Consider a length t sized set $X_{i \in I}$ such $|X| = t$. X has index $I = \{1, 2, 3 \dots t\}$. Now consider two sets A_n and B_m with index n and m respectively, such $n = \{1, 2, 3 \dots n\}$, and $m = \{1, 2, 3 \dots m\}$. It is important that $m \leq n \leq t$, such $|B| \leq |A| \leq |X|$, and $B \subseteq A \subseteq X$. Because if $t \leq n < m$ and it is wished to $X_{A_n - B_m}$ then $i \notin I$.*

So $m \leq n$, as the default. The scenario of the lemma can be understood as a regime shift happening at time $t = n$ and if $n < m$ then the point would be out of the time series index. Note this does not apply upon the situation where the $n \leq t$ and $m \leq t$, since this would mean the m would not be outside of the t index.

The regime process can be understood as such,

$$L_t^I \ \& \ U_t^I = \begin{cases} L_t^{RS_i} \ \& \ U_t^{RS_i} & \text{if } p_t < L_t^I \\ L_t^{RS_i} \ \& \ U_t^{RS_i} & \text{if } p_t > U_t^I \\ L_t^I \ \& \ U_t^I & \text{if } L_t^I < p_t < U_t^I \end{cases}$$

and if the function already is regime switched,

$$L_t^{RS_i} \ \& \ U_t^{RS_i} = \begin{cases} L_t^{RS_{i+1}} \ \& \ U_t^{RS_{i+1}} & \text{if } p_t < L_t^{RS_i} \\ L_t^{RS_{i+1}} \ \& \ U_t^{RS_{i+1}} & \text{if } p_t > U_t^{RS_i} \\ L_t^{RS_i} \ \& \ U_t^{RS_i} & \text{if } L_t^{RS_i} < p_t < U_t^{RS_i} \end{cases}$$

Finally the formulas for the initial state I and the regime switched state RS_i will be shown. The formulas are denoted as such, starting with L_t notation:

$$L_t^I = L(p_t, \lambda, n, t) = \left(1 - \frac{1}{t - (t - n)} \int_{t-n}^t \sigma^2_{YZ} \lambda\right) (\log p_t - \frac{1}{t - (t - n)} \int_{t-n}^t \sigma_{YZ})$$

and,

$$L_t^{RS_i} = L(p_t, \lambda, m, t) = \left(1 - \frac{1}{t - (t - m)} \int_{t-m}^t \sigma^2_{YZ} \lambda\right) (\log p_t - \frac{1}{t - (t - m)} \int_{t-m}^t \sigma_{YZ})$$

or,

$$L_t^I = L(p_t, \lambda, n, t) = \left(1 - \frac{1}{n} \int_{t-n}^t \sigma^2_{YZ} \lambda\right) (\log p_t - \frac{1}{n} \int_{t-n}^t \sigma_{YZ})$$

and,

$$L_t^{RS_i} = L(p_t, \lambda, m, t) = \left(1 - \frac{1}{m} \int_{t-m}^t \sigma^2_{YZ} \lambda\right) (\log p_t - \frac{1}{m} \int_{t-m}^t \sigma_{YZ})$$

finally,

$$L_t^I = L(p_t, \lambda, n, t) = (1 - \overline{\sigma^2_{nYZ}} \lambda) (\log p_t - \overline{\sigma_{nYZ}})$$

and,

$$L_t^{RS_i} = L(p_t, \lambda, m, t) = (1 - \overline{\sigma^2_{mYZ}} \lambda) (\log p_t - \overline{\sigma_{mYZ}})$$

and for U_t ,

$$U_t^I = U(p_t, \lambda, n, t) = \left(1 + \frac{1}{t - (t - n)} \int_{t-n}^t \sigma^2_{YZ} \lambda\right) (\log p_t + \frac{1}{t - (t - n)} \int_{t-n}^t \sigma_{YZ})$$

and,

$$U_t^{RS_i} = U(p_t, \lambda, m, t) = \left(1 + \frac{1}{t - (t - m)} \int_{t-m}^t \sigma^2_{YZ} \lambda\right) (\log p_t + \frac{1}{t - (t - m)} \int_{t-m}^t \sigma_{YZ})$$

or,

$$U_t^I = U(p_t, \lambda, n, t) = \left(1 + \frac{1}{n} \int_{t-n}^t \sigma^2_{YZ} \lambda\right) (\log p_t + \frac{1}{n} \int_{t-n}^t \sigma_{YZ})$$

and,

$$U_t^{RS_i} = U(p_t, \lambda, m, t) = \left(1 + \frac{1}{m} \int_{t-m}^t \sigma^2_{YZ} \lambda\right) (\log p_t + \frac{1}{m} \int_{t-m}^t \sigma_{YZ})$$

finally,

$$U_t^I = U(p_t, \lambda, n, t) = (1 + \overline{\sigma^2_{nYZ}} \lambda) (\log p_t + \overline{\sigma_{nYZ}})$$

and,

$$U_t^{RS_i} = U(p_t, \lambda, m, t) = (1 + \overline{\sigma_{mYZ}^2} \lambda)(\log p_t + \overline{\sigma_{mYZ}})$$

Thus this function will be run every steps to deem if price is within the regime. To understand the qualities and shortfalls of the model, it will now be deployed in a simulated environment. This is also done to get a visual look at the model.

3 Simulation

Figure 2: Picture of polymarket.com: Will the Iranian regime fall by June 30? Picture taken: 03/3/2026

Figure 3: Picture of polymarket.com: Kamilla Rakhimova vs Maria Timofeeva. Picture taken: 03/3/2026

The simulation serves the purpose of finding shortfalls and observing the fitting behavior of the boundaries in a moving prediction market. The simulation will be made with Python, within a Jupyter notebook, while use the libraries Numpy, Pandas, SciPy and Plotly for plotting.

On prediction markets it is observed that a market typically behaves in two different ways. As seen in figure 2, it displays a price path that resembles Brownian motion. This is behavior is more common in long term contracts. As seen in figure 3, it is showing a price path that resembles a Poisson process with almost no drift. This is more common behavior in short term sport contracts, where information jumps dominate the price of the contract.

It is also important to state that p_t will take the definition of a prediction market variable denoted as such.

$$X = \{X \in \mathbb{R} | 1 \leq X \leq 99\}$$

$$p_t \subseteq X$$

For access to the Jupyter notebook containing simulation code, and reproducibility specifications refer to (Samuel, 2026).

3.1 Price path simulation

For the simulation it is important to have a price path that is representative of what we are trying to model. The price path is split into historical and forward terms. This simulates the historical price data we need for the variance and volatility estimations, and the forward path we try to deploy the boundaries on. Therefore the simulation uses a stochastic process resembling a combination of Brownian motion, and a Poisson process. This allows us to tweak the parameters to get the price path to resemble the evolution of prediction markets contract prices. For a detailed understanding of the simulation please refer to the README in (Samuel, 2026).

3.2 Static boundary model

Price path with historical data with static boundary

Figure 4: Static boundaries: Green line at time 100 is where the historical and forward path split. The blue line is for p_t , and the red, and green line are for L_t and U_t .

The static boundary is defined by the fact it does not move when price is outside of the boundaries. As seen on figure 4, the boundaries have not moved with the current price. This can be understood as the base model, so L_t and U_t with no state notation. The static boundaries are useful in a market with little volatility. Figure 4 displays such a market where the price is around the 39c to 43c interval and the regime exist from about 43c to about 41c. From this we can conclude that the model falls apart as soon a more volatile market regime is introduced.

Price path with historical data with static boundary

Figure 5: Jump in price from 70c to about 99c simulating information jumps.

Figure 5 shows how the boundaries gets left behind and the price is now in a new regime. This would mean our current regime tell us nothing about the current state. In a non static model this would lead to a regime shift denoted with RS_i , but since it is static that does not happen. This will be further explored in section 3.4.

Price path with historical data with static boundary

Figure 6: Price path with no volatility.

Another problem presents itself with the fact that the model boundaries mainly employ variance and volatility to be created. This presents a problem with low volatility markets where if the volatility is 0 or close to zero the boundaries will not move or be big enough to accept any price as seen on figure 6. This means it has a requirement for volatility in order to be able to create a regime boundaries which is problematic in very low volatility markets. This can also become a problem if the look back time is not far enough and price has stagnated then it will also exhibit behavior like figure 6. This shows that the model exhibits problems with a zero to low volatility regimes, as this returns close to none in boundary width. With no boundary width, it makes interpreting the regimes exceedingly more difficult or impossible with the use of the model. Therefore the problem is the user lacks information about current regime volatility trends. This does not tell the user about how the market is quite illiquid or the market participants have decided on a price. A possible solution to always scale the boundaries, could be to employ the aforementioned $(1 \pm \lambda)$ as the first part of the model.

Price path with historical data with static boundary

Figure 7: Historical price path with high volatility, thus scaling boundaries

Price path with historical data with static boundary

Figure 8: Historical price path with high volatility , thus scaling boundaries.

The largest discovered shortfall of the static version is that the boundaries can scale to an undesirable amount if the look back periods volatility is very high, as seen of figure 7 and 8. This happens because the boundaries get scaled by volatility, therefore making them very wide in a high volatility regime. Normally this would be acceptable, as a traditional stock should be allowed to oscillate more in price, however on prediction markets, this is a different story, since the price can only be between 1 and 99 cent. Although this gives us a good snippet of the current market conditions, it lacks the auto-adjusting feature, thus it requires a different model to counteract the scaling boundaries,

3.3 Lambda

Price path with historical data with static boundary

Figure 9: Example of boundaries with lambda set to 1

Price path with historical data with static boundary

Figure 10: Example of boundaries with lambda set to 10

Before looking at models that counteract the scaling boundaries problem it is important to gain visual intuition of the lambda parameter. Looking at figure 9 and 10, it can be understood that lambda can widen and narrow the boundaries as long as it is above 0. So $\lambda > 0$. If $\lambda > 1$ the boundaries will widen, and opposite if $0 < \lambda < 1$ then the boundaries will narrow. Therefore it

needs to be understood that the first part of the model $(1 + \overline{\sigma_{nYZ}^2} \lambda)$, λ so it can be inferred that the effectiveness depends on the size of $\overline{\sigma_{nYZ}^2}$. While the impact of lambda is limited by the size of the variance, it is understood that lambda acts as a risk parameter, or determines how much oscillation is to be allowed in each regime. The aforementioned $(1 \pm \lambda)$ as a different interpretation of the first term, can be used if a more effective scaler is wished.

3.4 Dynamic model with rolling and without rolling boundaries

The dynamic model is defined with boundaries that perpetually define new regimes in a rolling and non-rolling manner. It should be understood that this is the I and RS_i version of the model. This has both a rolling version and a non-rolling version. The non-rolling version only shift the boundaries when they are exceeded, and will keep the original boundary from the current regimes $t - m$ time, until the boundaries are exceeded. This leaves the model with the chance of scaling boundaries again, thus introducing, the rolling version. The rolling version perpetually shift the boundaries to a moving $t - m$ point in time, thus making sure the current regime is fit to the predetermined \int_{t-m}^t look back time every t step, this means that the boundary will auto-adjust to extreme jumps and create a new regime. Another way to understand the rolling version is that each step, a new L_t and U_t gets calculated with look back time \int_{t-m}^t . The rolling version also creates new regimes when boundaries get broken. The initial state can be understood as the static version. Thus it is understood that, until a regime shift, all presented models are static.

3.4.1 Non-rolling version

Price path with historical data with dynamic boundary

Figure 11: The adjusted boundary after a regime shift.

Price path with historical data with dynamic boundary

Figure 12: The adjusted boundary after a regime shift

Price path with historical data with dynamic boundary

Figure 13: Forward price path with high volatility, thus scaling boundaries to an undesirable amount.

In figure 11 a RS_i boundary is seen. The RS_i boundaries are normally narrower in the dynamic version, since they typically have a shorter look back times, otherwise the regime shifts would have little impact on the new boundaries. Figure 12 displays a wider boundary at a later time t . This occurs in the situation where the look back variance and volatility is larger than in the previous regime or RS_{i-1} . This shows the auto-adjusting nature of the dynamic boundaries. Although even with this trait the non-rolling version fails to overcome the undesirable scaling boundaries as seen on figure 13. Thus the rolling version will be deployed to overcome these shortfalls.

3.4.2 Rolling version

Price path with historical data with dynamic boundary

Figure 14: The adjusted boundary after a regime shift.

Price path with historical data with dynamic boundary

Figure 15: A wide boundary after a big jump in price).

Price path with historical data with dynamic boundary

Figure 16: Fixed boundaries after a jump in price.

Figure 14-16 display the boundaries before and after an extreme boundary scaling event. This showcases the auto-adjusting nature of the dynamic rolling boundaries. This is the optimal version for perpetually understanding regimes on prediction markets. Although there is a trade-off when choosing this model. The main trade-off when doing this model is choosing the m look back time. It should be said that, if a price process exhibits Poisson behavior this model is very susceptible to be caught in a no volatility regime, where the boundaries will display no width as seen in figure 6.

With a short look back time the user will lose the data of previous price points, and gain boundaries that represents the current price quicker. This means even without a regime shift, it will only represent a short time-frame of the timeseries, if the look back time is short. This can be great on markets with a high frequency of information jumps, since the new boundaries will represent the regime accurately instead of taking old regime data into account. Note there is a problem with the short look back rolling model in markets that behave Poisson. A market that behaves Poisson typically exhibit low volatility in between the jumps. With a short look back time this would mean that $t - m$ time after an information jump, the boundaries would resemble what we see in figure

6. In this situation a non-rolling boundary would be better.

On the other hand with a longer look back time the user can gain a boundary that represent the time series more completely. This mean that the information jumps will be mediated by the bigger $\frac{1}{n}$ or $\frac{1}{m}$ factor. Although the scaling from information jumps will be mediated, the jump can still be so big that it still might scale to an undesirable level, or too wide in terms of the price restrictions. The longer look back time also means that boundaries confluence rather than being more independent. This look back time applies better to low volatility markets exhibiting Poisson process behavior, where it is important to get all the possible information an mediate the $\frac{1}{n}$ or $\frac{1}{m}$ factor.

The choice of model and solutions for these shortfalls will be discussed further in section 4.

4 Applications

The model employs useful across a wide variety of fields. The main application and the focus of this paper, is the models ability to define regimes on prediction markets. It can be used as an analytics tool for regime research. If the user requires a regime defining model for research on a specific set of time series data set the model can be applied. The model can be used for finding the amount how many regime shift happen within a window or how regimes look in different time frames. It also acts great as an analytics tool, as it does not only produce an arbitrary log number but also can be reversed back into the price index, making it more transparent. This makes it more interpretable and makes it better for plotting the results. The simulations also let it be inferred that the modularity of the model will allow the user to conduct the research more individually, instead of in a generalized sense. The parameters can also be viewed as negative, as it can cause confusion on how to navigate model, in order to produce a usable boundary. The regime models usefulness is not only for research purposes.

It can also be used for market making on prediction markets. Because of the probabilistic nature of prediction market contracts, the opportunity to quote the spread often presents itself (Bürigi et al., 2025). This phenomenon happens because of the absence of market makers, thus making the bid-ask spread more dependent on retail market participants. This makes price less stable allowing for a bid-ask spread that is subtle for even retail market making with fees. Thus the model can provide an interval where it is optimal to quote or for the market maker to have a sense of their inventories risk in the current regime. Thus the model can be employed to market make on prediction markets in multiple scenarios.

A down side to market making on prediction markets, is most markets have low liquidity. This leads to slow order fill times. This is the main factor that makes prediction markets suboptimal for market making, as profits will be slow on most markets. An upside is that if the arbitrageur quotes both the yes and no side contracts bid-ask spread, then the they will have a theoretical perfect hedge. This occurs because the inventory value on yes side coincide with the value of the no side, because of the binary structure of the markets (Kalshi, 2026). It should be mentioned that sometimes the price does not coincides if there is another outcome to the market like a tie event.

It understood from the simulations that the different versions of the model each has their own shortfalls. These shortfalls are hard to overcome with the presented version, thus using multiple models would prove useful. This in method the different models would cover for each-others shortfalls. A non-rolling long look back model and a rolling short look back model working asynchronously could be a solution, consider the following example of a dynamic model:

The long models purpose would be to have more regime data than the short, model and the short look back model would be deployed when the boundaries of the long look back model scale above the desired amount. This would cover the shortfall of a short look back time only presenting a small amount of the regime and a long look back representing the previous regime

Another application is for market making on traditional exchanges, or likewise crypto exchanges. The model functions on these markets since they provide time series data, that the model can leverage to make boundaries. It can also be used as a stop-loss or take profit on traditional markets. If the user seeks volatility-regime defined stop-loss or take profit, the model can function as that as well.

5 Conclusion

Conclusively it is found that the model presented in the paper provides a way for users to model the current regime of a financial time series. From the research it is understood that the presented model uses current price, volatility and variance to compute purely market derived boundaries. This process then defines a regime, that can be used to understand how much price should oscillate within the current defined regime, before determining the regime conditionally irrelevant to understand the next regimes market conditions. In turn this creates a upper and lower price interval. From the research it is also understood that the model takes in several parameters that allows the user to adjust risk, time series data inclusion and a price parameter. The model also uses multiple states to define the current regime which is used in the different versions of the model.

It was then discovered that the markets on prediction markets typically exhibit two kinds of behaviors, when it comes to contract price paths. One that resembles the path of Brownian motion and one that resembles a Poisson process. The simulation findings also showed that the model can be deployed in different ways. The static method showed a non-rolling boundary derived from the base formula. This static model showed great results while price was withing boundaries, however lacked the creation of new boundaries once the regime changed. It was also vulnerable to big price movements with it occasionally producing boundaries that scaled to an undesirable amount. It showed problems on the Poisson like process which is suboptimal for prediction markets. Therefore the dynamic model was introduced. The dynamic model offered a rolling and non-rolling version, with both models derived from the state version. The non-rolling dynamic model is restricted to changing boundaries when prices moves outside of the interval. This presented more desirable performance as it adjusted perpetually if price was undesirable, however it was still susceptible to boundaries scaling to an undesirable level. The rolling dynamic model was then the solution to fix the scaling boundaries. This version rescaled boundaries every step. This made it possible for the boundaries to rescale after n or m steps. This model lacked the representativeness of the time series data like the other models.

Throughout the research it was also found that the model not only functions on prediction markets but also has other use cases. The model could also have uses on traditional exchanges as well as on crypto exchanges. While mainly for modeling the regime, The model can also serve as a stop loss or take profit, as it defines a price interval that is acceptable for price to move between, and has parameters that allow for risk management. this can employ useful if it is important for understanding a certain market dynamics. The idea of combining models was also considered to cover for the models short falls.

Conclusively it can be said that the paper presented a model, which gives the framework for defining regimes on time series data.

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